

Noise shielding models for the conceptual design of unconventional aircraft

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ABSTRACT

Air traffic growth and the expansion of urban areas around airports make the aviation community noise a key aspect of aircraft design. The analysis of innovative configurations is becoming activity of primary interest within the scientific community. The current effort to attain the strict noise–abatement targets imposed by the authorities risks to be profitless without a significant technological breakthrough. A promising innovative configuration in terms of noise reduction is the Blended–Wing–Body aircraft. Indeed, the installation of the propulsion system above the centre–body surface ensures a significant masking effect of the engine noise components. The lack of experimental data needed to validate the advantages introduced by these technologies, and therefore carry out parametric analysis, can only be overcome by formulating reliable and cost–effective models to predict the noise shielding induced by engines installation on unconventional geometries. The present work introduces the development of tailored models for the correction of the existing semi-empirical prediction techniques. Such models are embedded within the modules of the existing conceptual design framework FRIDA. Without excluding other disciplines, the introduction of a noise prediction tool allows to cast a wide net in the research of optimal configuration in the future aviation context.

1 Introduction

Community–noise related to aircraft and airport is a complex subject which has been studied for decades and still represents a principal issue for many research effort nowadays. There exist several authorities involved in pursuing a program of aircraft noise control through standards which impose, in particular, certain takeoff and landing procedures. The FAA has an active program [1], *The Continuous Lower Energy, Emissions, and Noise* (CLEEN) program, to advance the development of technologies to further reduce noise from aircraft. In February 2013, the *International Civil Aviation Organization’s* (ICAO’s) *Committee on Aviation Environmental Protection*

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(CAEP) agreed on a new global noise reduction standard [2]. In order to achieve this strict target, a technological breakthrough in aircraft concepts is necessary.

Ideas about noise shielding obtained installing the engines on top of the fuselage have been conceived for both conventional and innovative aircraft configurations. Results of high-level simulations have shown that a large surface is needed to make this installation effect effective. For this and many other reasons, in the last decade configurations such as Blended-Wing-Body (BWB) have met with success at research interest. At first, its large centre body surface, shaped as an airfoil, contributes to the overall lift force enhancing the aerodynamic efficiency [3] and, at the same time, allows to accommodate a high number of passengers. Another advantage introduced by this configuration is the herein discussed on top engine installation [4] that appeals researchers in view of urban-noise benefits.

The test-case chosen in this paper for the assessment of noise shielding is a target aircraft carrying about 100 passengers, as such aircraft accounts for more than 90 percent of global emissions from commercial fleet worldwide [5]. In particular, this work focuses on the development of a model for the evaluation of the noise shielding effect of BWB configurations to be included within analysis and optimisation tools for the multidisciplinary conceptual design.

For conventional configurations, experimental data for lateral attenuation are available in existing semi-empirical analysis tools. Conversely, when studying a non-conventional configuration, such information is not available and performing direct-simulations would be excessively cost-demanding. Focusing on standard airport procedures' simulations, analysis tool requires a large number of evaluation points for the acoustic certification of BWB aircraft in its mission path so that an alternative to high-fidelity simulations for noise characterisation needs to be included. Since many years, several techniques have been developed [6] to assess surrogate models which are equivalent to the set of data obtained through simulations: depending on the nature of the problem, the best procedure and tools can be identified.

In this work, an approach based on the well-known Kriging method has been chosen to build a surrogate model (*i.e.*, metamodel) to be implemented within the existing in-house Multidisciplinary Conceptual Robust Design Optimisation (MCRDO) framework FRIDA (FRamework for Innovative Design in Aeronautics, for details see the APPENDIX). In particular, FRIDA can handle both acoustic certification analysis and trajectory optimisation. Depending on the purpose, a different number of degree-of-freedom has to be considered to train the metamodel: for certification analyses, a small number of degree-of-freedom (corresponding to the sampled aircraft path) is sufficient, whereas, in case of trajectory optimisation, a wider number of microphone for the assessment of an extended acoustic field must be included. Herein a wide acoustic field is considered in order to assess the feasibility study of metamodels for trajectory optimisation. As matter of fact, an important aspect of the present approach is the identification of the minimum number of degree-of-freedom, in the design space, to be evaluated by means of direct simulations as a compromise between accuracy/reliability and computation effort for the construction of the metamodel.

The Ffowcs Williams-Hawking equation for the scattered pressure field is presented in Section 2, with some details on the kriging method. In Section 3, assumptions on the basis of the metamodel for the noise shielding are detailed. Numerical results are presented in Section 4. Section 5 closes the paper with some concluding remarks.

2 Theoretical background

One of the Blended-Wing-Body peculiarity lies on the possibility to mount the engines on top of the centre-body lifting surface. Such characteristic makes the sound energy of some engine noise components less intense due to the shielding effect. The acoustic describer for the noise shielding effect characterisation is the Insertion-Loss (IL). In the frequency domain, it can be defined as it

follows

$$IL = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\tilde{p}_I}{\tilde{p}_T} \right) = SPL_I - SPL_T \quad (1)$$

where $\tilde{p}_T = \tilde{p}_I + \tilde{p}_S$ is the total pressure, \tilde{p}_I the incident pressure, \tilde{p}_S the scattered pressure and SPL is the sound pressure level. Pressure data are computed through numerical simulations carried out using a validated in-house code implementing a formulation for the scattered pressure field based on the Ffowcs Williams–Hawking equation. Defining the wave number $k = \omega/c_0$ (with c_0 the sound velocity and ω the angular frequency) and the propagation time θ , the integral representation of the scattered acoustic field at the *virtual* microphone location \mathbf{x} due to a source placed in \mathbf{y} is given by the following equation[7]

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{p}'_S(\mathbf{x}, k) = & - \int_S \left[\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \hat{G} - ikc_0 \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \theta \hat{G} \right] \tilde{p}'_I(\mathbf{y}, k) e^{-ik \frac{c_0}{\theta}} dS \\ & - \int_S \left[\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \hat{G} - ikc_0 \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \theta \hat{G} \right] \tilde{p}'_S(\mathbf{y}, k) e^{-ik \frac{c_0}{\theta}} dS \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

being \hat{G} the Green function. In this work, the solution of the Equation 2 is provided by a zero-th order boundary element method solver.

The noise shielding effect prediction of the BWB configuration, if addressed using the approach described above, leads to a prohibitive computational burden. Consequently, a strategy based on metamodels build-up seems to be more appropriate. The main advantage of using a surrogate model in the process of designing a new concept of vehicle is the reduction of timing-costs in perspective of conceptual design optimisation. An important aspect of this approach is the reliability of the obtained metamodel and how it well-represents the simulated phenomena as the final choice of the designer is based on the result of analyses where these databases are involved. In this work, the surrogate model is built using the well-known kriging method[8, 9], based on a zero-th order regression, which corresponds to an ordinary kriging.

The kriging goal is to predict the value $\hat{y}(\mathbf{x})$ given $y(\mathbf{x}_1), \dots, y(\mathbf{x}_{N_s})$, where N_s is the available number of experiments (*i.e.* numerical simulations). Let formalize the response of the model as it follows

$$y = \mathbf{f}^T \beta + \mathbf{Z} \quad (3)$$

being \mathbf{Z} a stochastic process which follows the normal distribution, *i.e.* with zero expectation and variance σ^2 . By choosing a certain correlation function R , the $N_s \times N_s$ covariance matrix \mathbf{R} of \mathbf{Z} can be expressed as

$$\text{Cov} [Z(\mathbf{x}_i), Z(\mathbf{x}_j)] = \sigma^2 \mathbf{R} [R(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j)] \quad (4)$$

where $i = 1, \dots, N_s$ and $j = 1, \dots, N_s$. It is easy to understand that if the distance $\|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|$ is small, $y(\mathbf{x}_j)$ tends to be close to $y(\mathbf{x}_i)$, provided that there are no discontinuities in the function. Regarding the choice of R , several studies[10, 11] provide a detailed description of different correlation functions: a choice often found in literature[12] is the exponential correlation function, *i.e.*

$$R(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) = \exp \left(- \sum_{k=1}^{N_s} \theta_k |\mathbf{x}_{i_k} - \mathbf{x}_{j_k}|^{p_k} \right) \quad (5)$$

where p_k determines the smoothness of the correlation in the k -th direction[9] and θ_k is the vector collecting the correlation parameters. Note that if $\|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\| \rightarrow \infty$ then $R \rightarrow 0$, and of course when $\|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\| = 0$ the correlation R equals 1. Using this approach, it is possible to predict $\hat{y}(\mathbf{x})$ as it follows

$$\hat{y}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{f}^T \beta + \mathbf{r}^T(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{R}^{-1} (\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{F} \beta) \quad (6)$$

being \mathbf{Y} the function values at the N_s training points, \mathbf{F} the basis functions and \mathbf{r} the vector containing the spatial correlation terms. By means of a least-square estimation, it is possible to estimate $\hat{\beta}$ as

$$\hat{\beta} = (\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{F}) \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{Y} \quad (7)$$

and then, combining the Equations 6 and 7, the evaluation $\hat{y}(\mathbf{x})$ is provided as a function of the N_s available data, evaluated with the direct numerical simulations.

The kriging implementation, used for the present study, exploits a Matérn covariance function with $\nu = 1/2$ (the parameter ν governs the smoothness and differentiability of the covariance function), a global optimisation method (with fixed search directions) to determine the parameter values and the likelihood function to compare the plausibility of these parameter values[13].

3 Surrogate model build-up

Aim of the metamodel definition is its inclusion in the in-house MCRDO framework FRIDA (for detail, see the APPENDIX), in which prime-principle-based analysis along with an efficient flight simulator provide the input of well-assessed semi-empirical 1/3 octave bands aeroacoustic models for the noise prediction. For a given frequency f , the time-dependent shielding effect of a lifting surface is a function of the engine position \mathbf{x}_E , the flight Mach number M , in addition to the aircraft-observer relative position (defined by the distance r and the directivity angles θ and ϕ). The number of points that yields a reliable model is frequency dependent: as the noise field frequency increases, the number of evaluation points required for catching the wave length increases as well. On the other hand, the higher the frequency, the stronger the atmospheric attenuation effects. Consequently, the contribution of the higher frequencies on the overall energy is gradually negligible. In this regard, a further analysis is necessary to identify the frequency range of interest when studying the perceived-noise subject so that the number of degree-of-freedom can be reduced. In this context, the selection of training points for the metamodel construction seems to be a key aspect, since the characterisation of the noise-shielding behaviour over an entire mission would require a huge amount of numerical high-fidelity numerical simulations. With the purpose of making acceptable the metamodel construction computational cost, without forgoing the prediction reliability, several assumptions have been made.

First of all, although the scattered field directivity pattern is highly affected by the propulsion system location, the elementary source that represents it has been chosen on the basis of sketches available in literature. The source location is shown in Figure 1 and must be interpreted as the expectation of \mathbf{x}_E .

Let also analyse, for the sake of simplicity, a standard 2D takeoff operation, *i.e.* such that $\phi = 0^\circ$ (simulated using the framework FRIDA), for an airplane similar to the high-capacity regional BWB, case study of the present work. The time envelope of the noise descriptors at a virtual microphone located at the takeoff-flyover certification point is shown in Figure 2.

For each curve, due to the Decibel summation process, the more distant are the values from the maximum peak, the smaller is the influence on the integrated value. In addition, as it is known, the duration correction of the Effective Perceived Noise Level EPNL (required for the aircraft acoustic certification) is computed starting from the knowledge of the time interval during which the PNdB values do not fall below the 10 PNdB threshold with respect to the maximum value of the tone-corrected perceived noise level[14]. It is interesting to note how, giving the above, the direct simulations for the evaluation of the metamodel training points can be sampled into a significantly reduced subdomain, as shown in Figure 3.

As it has been said above, preserving the possibility of simulating even slightly different maneuvers for the purpose of including the noise shielding into trajectory optimisation analyses, the authors have chosen to stretch-out the required subdomain. For each frequency under analysis and

Figure 1: Top view (a) and side view (b) of the configuration used for BEM simulations: BWB geometry (blue) and point-source position (yellow) used for building the evaluation of the scattered pressure field.

Figure 2: Noise descriptors (estimated with semi-empirical models) as a function of the time of a standard takeoff operation for a 100-pax conventional aircraft.

for three values of Mach ($M = 0.2$, $M = 0.3$ and $M = 0.4$), the shielding effect has been computed, with the BEM solution of the Equation 2, over a ring-arc grid ($0^\circ < \theta < 180^\circ$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$) under the aircraft: the grid is centered on \mathbf{x}_E , and the minimum radius r_{min} has been set equal to $800m$ whereas the maximum radius r_{max} is $4.8km$. The positions of the virtual microphones inside the ring arc have been chosen with standard triangulation method.

4 Results and discussion

In this section, the results obtained applying the kriging method are shown and compared with direct simulations in order to verify the metamodel reliability in the acoustic field reconstruction. Below, for sake of clarity, the reported results are related to the 1/3 octave band centre-frequency $f = 100Hz$. The results from direct simulations (at the three different Mach numbers) were used to train the kriging algorithm and the resulting IL maps shown below correspond to the values extrapolated at $M = 0.25$ and $M = 0.35$.

In Figure 4 the insertion-loss maps, evaluated by means of the BEM solution of Equation 2,

Figure 3: Aircraft–observer relative distance r (blue), polar angle θ (red) and Mach number M (black) as functions of the time, relative to the subdomain needed for the metamodel aimed at simulating the noise shielding effect over the analysed takeoff operation.

are shown. These results, accurate in terms of spatial resolution, are used as reference for the comparison with the surrogate models.

Figure 4: Reference IL maps obtained from direct simulation with in–house BEM solver for $M = 0.25$ and $M = 0.35$.

Figure 5(a) shows the BEM solutions at 339 training points. The kriging algorithm has been applied and the prediction on the same points as for the reference case is shown in Figure 5(b).

Figure 6(a) show the BEM representations at 614 virtual microphones. Note that the BEM accuracy is the same of the previous case. Once again, the kriging algorithm has been applied to the training set, and the predicted values on the same points as for the reference case are shown in Figure 6(b).

It is worth noting that, for all the analysed frequencies, the accuracy of the kriging prediction seems rather inadequate because of the chosen high number of degree–of–freedom and the strong gradient which the function is characterised by. Furthermore, the accuracy of the surrogate model has shown to be highly dependent on the velocity variable resolution rather than on the spatial resolution. This can be attributed to the unpredictable behaviour of the scattering phenomenon, due to the complexity of the geometrical model and the variability of the solution with regards to the body speed between the data sets given to the modeler. Even though the predicted values don’t reproduce exactly the IL maps, the overall effects are globally caught. Moreover, from Figures 5

Figure 5: Training points IL maps (a) built using 339 points obtained with direct simulation at $M = 0.20$ (left), $M = 0.30$ (centre) and $M = 0.40$ (right), and Kriging metamodel results (b) carried out from the 339 training points extrapolated for $M = 0.25$ (left) and $M = 0.35$ (right).

Figure 6: Training points IL maps (a) built using 614 points obtained with direct simulation at $M = 0.20$ (left), $M = 0.30$ (centre) and $M = 0.40$ (right), and Kriging metamodel results (b) carried out from the 614 training points extrapolated for $M = 0.25$ (left) and $M = 0.35$ (right).

and 6 it can be evinced that the kriging prediction algorithm is dominated by the deterministic term which influences the results at extrapolated speed.

5 Conclusions

In this work, the criteria of generating a surrogate model to include scattering effects of the novel BWB configuration within a multidisciplinary analysis and optimisation tool have been described. The shielding effect in presence of flow has been assessed using the integral representation of the scattered acoustic field in the frequency domain (Ffowcs Williams–Hawking equation): the solutions have been numerically provided by a zero-th order Boundary–Element–Method solver. The results of the numerical simulations have been used for the attempt of building a surrogate model by means of the kriging approach. Several assumptions have been made with the purpose of making the prediction reliable and keeping acceptable the metamodel construction computational cost. Results have shown that the kriging formulation is not efficient for the acoustic field metamodeling oriented to trajectory optimisation problems. The reasons are mainly attributed to the predominance of the deterministic term in the kriging formulation with respect to the stochastic part as well as the complexity of the considered aircraft geometry which makes unpredictable the scattering behaviour for each speed at every frequency. Despite the aforementioned issues, the prediction has demonstrated to globally catch the fundamental features of the scattering phenomenon.

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APPENDIX: the MCRDO framework FRIDA

The Multidisciplinary Conceptual Robust Design Optimisation (MCRDO) framework FRIDA (FRamework for Innovative Design in Aeronautics) has been used for the analyses presented in this paper. The implemented algorithms are, whenever possible, prime-principle based so that FRIDA is suitable for applications that require the aircraft configuration definition and the environmental impact estimation of both conventional and unconventional aircraft.

The aerodynamic model is based on quasi-potential flow theory [15] and the numerical solution is provided by a zeroth-order BEM, with a boundary-layer integral model to take into account the effects of viscosity. The flight mechanics verifies the static longitudinal stability of the aircraft, by imposing the derivative of the pitching moment (with respect to the centre of gravity) less than zero. The structural weight evaluation is assessed starting from the knowledge of the characteristic dimensions of the wing elements and the centre-body geometric sketch (engines landing gear and fixed equipment are successively added). The approximate modes of vibration are calculated with a FEM (Finite Element Method) model of the wing. The solution of the structural problem allows to obtain the diagonal matrix Ω of the natural frequencies of an equivalent beam representing the wing. By determining the nodal generalized forces due to the aerodynamic loads, the direct and shear stresses are also evaluated. The flutter and divergence speeds are also estimated using a reduced order model (ROM) based on a finite-state approximation for the evaluation of the matrix collecting the aerodynamic forces [16]. With a semi-empirical turbofan model, the engine operating point is predicted: the jet velocities are calculated through the momentum equation and jet temperatures are estimated with the energy balance. The mass of fuel burnt is also estimated in order to update the current aircraft weight over the trajectory simulation. The aeroacoustic module evaluates the airframe noise [17, 18], the fan/compressor noise [19] and the buzz-saw noise [20] as a function of the distance from the observers, the directivity angles, in

addition to the the actual wet surface and engine operating-point. The jet-noise is evaluated by means of polynomial regressions of experimental data. The current 1/3 octave band Sound Pressure Level (SPL) takes into account the Doppler effect, the atmospheric absorption [21] and the ground reflection. In addition, FRIDA implements an original sound-quality assessment method [22, 23, 24, 25], developed during the EC-funded projects SEFA (Sound Engineering For Aircraft, FP6, 2004–2007) and COSMA (Community Noise Solutions to Minimise aircraft noise Annoyance, FP7, 2009–2012). The recently-implemented noise-shielding metamodel for the unconventional BWB configuration is currently under development.

Several optimisation algorithms are implemented in FRIDA: the sparse-SQP (Sequential Quadratic Programming [26, 27]), the Genetic Algorithm **FORTRAN GA** [28], the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm **NSGA-II**[29] and a multi-objective Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO) algorithm [30] developed by the *Resistance & Optimisation team* of the CNR-INSEAN (characterised by the particles deterministic initialisation[31, 32]).